

A NOTE ON DRIS CONJECTURE

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we show that Dris conjecture on odd perfect numbers is true.

1. INTRODUCTION

The existence of odd perfect numbers has been a long-sought-after question, and despite centuries of search, nobody has found an example of an odd perfect number, nor can anyone find a proof that no odd perfect numbers can exist yet.

However, in addition to the existence of odd perfect numbers, several minor conjectures have also been made for odd perfect numbers. For example, Dris(2008) has conjectured that if n is an odd perfect number such that $n = q^a m^2$ with q being a prime number and $n \equiv q \equiv a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, and m is a positive integer, then we have $q^a < m$. [2] Brown(2016) has given a partial proof of Dris conjecture [1]; besides Starni(2018) has shown the following result that if n has $\omega(n)$ prime factors, and $M = \max\{\omega(n), a\}$, then we have the following relationship between q and m [4]:

$$(1) \quad \frac{1}{2}q^M < m^2.$$

In this paper, we present a proof of Dris conjecture. Unless otherwise specified, $\sigma(n)$ is the divisor function of a positive integer n , and under this definition, a perfect number is a positive integer such that $\sigma(n) = 2n$.

2. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 2.1. *Let $n = q^a m^2$ be an odd perfect number with q being a prime number and $n \equiv q \equiv a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, and m be a positive integer, then $q^a < m$.*

Proof. First, we have the following inequality by Dris(2012) [3]:

$$(2) \quad L < \frac{\sigma(q^a)}{q^a} + \frac{\sigma(m^2)}{m^2} \leq U$$

where $\frac{57}{20} \leq 3 - \frac{q-2}{q(q-1)} = L$ and $U = 3 - \frac{q-1}{q(q+1)} \leq 3$

Assume that $m \leq \sigma(q^a)$, then we have

$$(3) \quad \frac{m}{q^a} + \frac{\sigma(m^2)}{m^2} < \frac{\sigma(q^a)}{q^a} + \frac{\sigma(m^2)}{m^2} < U.$$

By multiplying $q^a m$ on both sides, then (3) implies that

$$(4) \quad m^2 - Uq^a m + C < 0$$

where $C = \frac{q^a \sigma(m^2)}{m}$

By solving (4) for m , if $0 \leq U^2q^{2a} - 4C = U^2q^{2a} - \frac{4q^a\sigma(m^2)}{m}$, then we have

$$(5) \quad \frac{1}{2}(Uq^a - \sqrt{U^2q^{2a} - \frac{4q^a\sigma(m^2)}{m}}) < m < \frac{1}{2}(Uq^a + \sqrt{U^2q^{2a} - \frac{4q^a\sigma(m^2)}{m}}).$$

However, $0 \leq U^2q^{2a} - \frac{4q^a\sigma(m^2)}{m}$ implies that

$$(6) \quad \frac{U^2q^am}{4} \leq \sigma(m^2),$$

By multiplying $\sigma(q^a)$ on both sides of (6), we have

$$(7) \quad \frac{U^2q^am}{4}\sigma(q^a) \leq \sigma(n) = 2n = 2q^am^2.$$

But since $\frac{57}{20} \leq L < U$, (7) implies that

$$(8) \quad \sigma(q^a) \leq \frac{8}{U^2}m < m,$$

which contradicts the assumption that $m \leq \sigma(q^a)$, therefore, $U^2q^{2a} - 4C = U^2q^{2a} - \frac{4q^a\sigma(m^2)}{m} < 0$ and (4) can't have a solution for m , but (4) having no solution implies that the original assumption that $m \leq \sigma(q^a)$ is false. Therefore, we have $\sigma(q^a) < m$.

Since $q^a < \sigma(q^a)$, this implies that $q^a < \sigma(q^a) < m$. \square

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